

Designing and Controlling a Hybrid Fuel Cell System for Propelling a Turboprop Aircraft

Angelo De Donato*, Paolo Aliberti*, Marco Sorrentino*, Fabrizio Cuomo°, Carmine Musto°

Outline

- Hybrid-aircraft related research context and objectives
 - Opportunities linked to PEMFC&Li-ion battery technologies
- Modeling approach
- Strategic design and operating requirements definition
- Degradation aware control
- Dynamic programming validation on a realistic electric propulsion load trajectory
- Conclusions and future activities

Background

- In 2023, aviation accounted for 2.5% of global energy-related CO₂ emissions, approaching 950 Mt CO₂, more than 90% of pre-Covid-19 levels¹;
- Such a figure must be reduced to cope with the 2050 Net Zero Emissions scenario. Alternative propulsion systems and fuels shall be investigated².

1: Lo Bue, R., <https://www.scienzainrete.it/articolo/rotta-verso-decarbonizzazione-dellaviazione-civile/riccardo-lo-bue/2023-10-06> 06/2023

2: Commission of the European Communities: "Hydrogen-powered aviation report", Clean Sky 2 JU and FCH 2 JU, 2020

Motivations for a Hybrid Propulsion System

- Fuel cells generate electricity with only water and heat as byproducts. Using green hydrogen ensures zero well-to-wheel emissions;
- Fuel cells exhibit higher efficiency compared to thermal engines, which can consequently be downsized or operated at their point of minimal fuel consumption and emissions.

Why Fuel cells?

Higher specific energy compared to batteries

Why batteries?

Load fluctuation
Fuel Cell low efficiency at high power

Workflow

Hybrid Electric Powertrain Architecture

- EN → Electrical node
- MN → mechanical node

- The **PEMFCS** requires moderate power fluctuation, therefore a battery pack is necessary;
- The **battery** mainly satisfies the power peaks, while it could be recharged in-flight via the PEMFCS.

$$M_{electric} = M_{batt} + M_{FCs} + M_{tank} + M_{H_2};$$

$$V_{electric} = V_{batt} + V_{FCs} + V_{tank};$$

$$P_{batt} = \frac{P_{EM}}{0.9} - P_{FCs}; P_{EM} = 2100 \text{ kW}; N_{BC} = \frac{P_{batt}}{P_{BC}};$$

$$DH_{electrical} = \frac{P_{batt}}{P_{batt} + P_{FCs}}$$

Workflow

Blended Rule-Based Control Strategy

$$P_{dem} = P_m = \text{electric motor power}$$

Selected Configuration: B1DH79²

- **B1:** Battery specific energy 300 Wh/kg;
- **DH:** degree of hybridization equal to 0.79

$$DH = \frac{P_{Batt}}{P_{Batt} + P_{FCS}}$$

¹ Sorrentino, M., Rizzo, G., Arsie, I., "Analysis of a rule-based control strategy for on-board energy management of series hybrid vehicles", *Control Engineering Practice*, Volume 19, pp. 1433-1441, 2011.

²Sparano, M., Sorrentino, M., Troiano, G., Cerino, G., Piscopo, G., Basaglia, M., & Pianese, C. (2023). The future technological potential of hydrogen fuel cell systems for aviation and preliminary co-design of a hybrid regional aircraft powertrain through a mathematical tool. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 281, 116822.

Control Maps Update

- The **PEMFCS efficiency curve** was updated to match Clean Hydrogen's SRIA power density requirement at 0.65 V [1];
- The rule-based control maps were modified accordingly.

[1] CLEAN HYDROGEN JU, Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda 2021 – 2027, <https://www.clean-hydrogen.europa.eu/system/files/2022-02/Clean%20Hydrogen%20SRIA%20-%20approved%20by%20GB%20-%20clean%20for%20publication%20%28ID%2013246486%29.pdf>.

Updated Control Strategy: Results

The high J efficiency curve implies **12%** increase in hydrogen consumption compared to low J scenario. This affects **FE**, which reduces by **5.36%**.

B1DH79	High J	Low J
M_{H_2} [kg] (gross*)	36.20	32.26
FE [km/kg]	19.93	21.06
P_{batt} [kW]	1833	
M_{batt}	1927	
$C_{batt,tot}$ [kW]	578	
$P_{PEMFCS,max}$ [kW]	500	
SOC_{in} [-]	0.95	
SOC_{min} [-]	0.19	
SOC_{end} [-]		
E_{H_2} [kWh]*	1189	1060
$E_{consbatt}$ [kWh]	440	445

*Needed plus emergency (+20%)

Workflow

Updated Degradation-aware Control Strategy

- Start-up/Shut downs and rapid transients represent critical operating conditions for PEMFCS, leading to membrane degradation, mechanical and thermal stresses, and excessive relative humidity;
- The control strategy is further modified by introducing an idling power level, while constraining the PEMFCS power slope.

$$SR = 10\%/s \cdot P_{PEMFCS,nom}$$
$$P_{idl} = P_{PEMFCS}(\eta_{max})$$

Workflow

Dynamic Programming Set-up

(a) Hybrid mode

- $P_{batt} > 0$
- $P_{FC} > 0$
- $P_{req} > 0$

(b) Recharge mode

- $P_{batt} < 0$
- $P_{FC} > 0$
- $P_{req} > 0$

Control variable:

$$u = \frac{P_{PEMFCs}}{P_{PEMFCs,nom}} \in [0,1]$$

State variable:

SOC

$$\min_{u(t)} \left(G(SOC(t_f)) + \int_{t_0}^{t_f} \dot{m}_{H_2}(SOC(t), u(t), t) dt \right)$$

Dynamic Programming-based Validation

B1DH79	RB	DP
M_{H_2} [kg] (gross*)	36.13	36
$M_{H_2,tank}$ [kg]	240.87	240
P_{batt} [kW]	1833	
$P_{PEMFCs,max}$ [kW]	500	
SOC_{in} [-]	0.95	
SOC_{min} [-]	0.2	
SOC_{end} [-]		
E_{H_2} [kWh]*	1187	1182
$E_{consbatt}$ [kWh]	435	

*Needed plus emergency (+20%)

Workflow

Masses and Volumes

B1DH79 - TOTAL MASS = 2454.13 KG

B1DH79 - TOTAL VOLUME = 2187.73 L

Parameters	Value	Source
PEMFCS gravimetric power density	2 [kW/kg]	[1]
PEMFCS volumetric power density	0.85 [kW/L]	[2]
Tank gravimetric capacity	15 [%weight]	[1]
Tank volumetric capacity	0.040 [kg/L]	[2]

[1] CLEAN HYDROGEN JU, Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda 2021 – 2027, <https://www.clean-hydrogen.europa.eu/system/files/2022-02/Clean%20Hydrogen%20JU%20SRIA%20-%20approved%20by%20GB%20-%20clean%20for%20publication%20%28ID%2013246486%29.pdf>

[2] Sparano, M., Sorrentino, M., Troiano, G., Cerino, G., Piscopo, G., Basaglia, M., & Pianese, C. (2023). The future technological potential of hydrogen fuel cell systems for aviation and preliminary co-design of a hybrid regional aircraft powertrain through a mathematical tool. Energy Conversion and Management, 281, 116822.

Conclusions

- A **hybrid electric unit**, including a proton exchange membrane **fuel cell system** and **battery**, for **hybrid regional aircraft** was investigated. Particularly, a **high degree of hybridization (i.e., high battery power)** scenario was analyzed;
- A **blended rule-based control** strategy was proposed and updated according to **up-to-date** fuel cell system **power density** requirements;
- **Degradation-aware control actions** were introduced, while validating the results via benchmarking against **dynamic programming**;
- **Masses, volumes and battery energy management meet** strategic research requirements.
- **Future studies** will encompass:
 - (i) Optimized hybrid electric unit sizing according to mass and volume constraints;
 - (ii) Techno-economic investigation of the most suitable degree of hybridization;
 - (iii) Degradation-aware design.

Contact Info

Thank you

- Marco Sorrentino
- University of Salerno
- Via Giovanni Paolo II 132, Fisciano (SA) 84084-Italy
- Phone +39089964100
- msorrentino@unisa.it